

AN EMPIRICAL ASSESSMENT OF CAUSES & EFFECTS OF DELAY IN RESIDENTIAL CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS IN HARARE, ZIMBABWE

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ABSTRACT

Construction delay is one of the major problems faced by the construction industry in Zimbabwe. Understanding the causes and effects of construction delay is important to minimize and or avoid the impact of delay in residential construction projects in Zimbabwe. This research seeks to empirically determine the causes and effects of delay in construction projects in Zimbabwe. From the analysis of the questionnaire, causes and effects of delay were ranked using the Relative Importance Index (RII) approach. The overall results analysis indicate that poor financial control on site, ineffective budgeting schedule and ineffective site management are amongst the most factors causing delays. The results also indicate that time overrun and cost overruns are the most important effects of delay in residential construction projects in Zimbabwe. Frequent meetings of all parties, effective planning and proper estimation of initial project cost are amongst the recommended ways of minimizing delays in residential construction projects in Zimbabwe.

Key Words: Construction industry, Delay, Relative Importance Index, Residential Construction, Zimbabwe

1. INTRODUCTION

Delay could be defined as the time overrun & cost overrun either beyond completion date specified in a contract or beyond the date that the parties agree upon for delivery of a project (Assaf & Al-Hejji, 2006). Due to the nature, size, complexity and technology advancement most of the projects are completed beyond the forecasted completion date (Arditi & Pattanakitchamroon, 2006). Delays are insidious often resulting in time overrun, cost overrun, disputes, litigation, and complete abandonment of projects (Sambasivan & Soon, 2007). Delay is a recurring incidence that can occur in almost every project carried out by any industry if appropriate project management knowledge is not employed (Shishu *et al*, 2014).

Delays are common in various construction projects and cause considerable losses to project parties (Anees & Sabarinathan, 2016). These delays also differ from project to project and from country to country (Pinto *et al*, 2011). Many projects are of such a nature that the client will suffer hardship, expense, or loss of revenue if the work is delayed beyond the time specified in the contract (Clough, 1986). The on-time completion of the projects is one of the most important factors of project success and a number of factors are contributing towards project success (Abbasid *et al*, 2015; Masa'deh *et al*, 2015; Orozco *et al*, 2015; Tarhini *et al*, 2015). In order to complete

construction projects on time and within the limits, proper project management is required in terms of minimizing or eliminating delays.

The role of economy growth in any country is highly affected by construction industry (Bangash, 2016). Due to its forward and backward linkages with other industries (Durdyev & Ismail, 2012), construction industry plays a very important role in providing the required infrastructure to improve the quality of life (Durdyev *et al*, 2017).

In Zimbabwe, the construction industry has the potential to account for at least 20% of the country's annual GDP (World Bank, 2016). The sector was set to grow by 1.5% in 2012 and create new job opportunities (Nyakazeya, 2012). According to ZimStat (2014), the construction industry contributed almost 3% to national GDP for the year 2014. ZimAsset (2013)'s growth projections indicate that the construction industry is expected to grow as high as 15% (of GDP) by 2018. Sustainable development of construction industry is therefore important (Enshassi & Ayyash, 2014), which has a multiplier impact on the wider economy (Durdyev & Ismail, 2016). However, the contribution of the construction sector in Zimbabwe is compromised when delays occur and according to Lin-Yin *et al* (2006), one significant problem is significant delay of infrastructure and construction projects which can hold back or impair planned economic development.

Delay is the most prominent difficulty faced in the construction sector in Zimbabwe. Frequent and lengthy delay of construction projects, as noted by Nyoni & Bonga (2017), has almost become a normal way of doing business in Zimbabwe. Timely and within budget completion of a construction project is frequently seen as a major criterion of project success by clients, contractors, consultants and related stakeholders (Luka & Muhammad, 2014; Ibrahim & Nabil, 2013; Abadir & Yimam, 2011; Chabota *et al*, 2008).

The primary objective of any residential construction project, just like any other construction project, is to complete the construction on time and within budget. However, this fundamental objective is compromised when delays occur and according to Sweis *et al* (2008), construction delays are often responsible for turning profitable projects into loss-making ventures.

Construction delays, as agitated by Megha & Bhatt (2013), have an adverse impact on project sponsor, client, project team member and participant involved in the entire project, which frequently result in disagreement, suspicion, financial problems and claims, lawsuit and negotiations. In the same line of thought, it is important to note that there is currently a critical shortage of housing in the city of Harare. Harare is the capital city of Zimbabwe and is currently highly populated and hence the need for more housing. Therefore, delay is a stumbling block to both construction companies and their clients.

Construction companies in Zimbabwe would be able to eliminate these delays if major contributing causes and subsequent effects were identified and planned for in time. This research

seeks to identify and rank the relative importance of delay causes and effects as perceived by consultants, contractors, owners and industry experts.

1.1 Objectives

- a. To identify the causes of delay in residential construction projects in Zimbabwe
- b. To determine the relative rank in terms of importance of each delay factor identified in a. above
- c. To identify the effects of delays
- d. To determine the relative rank in terms of importance of each delay effect identified in c. above

2. PREVIOUS STUDIES

In India, Anees & Sabarinathan (2016) carried out a study whose aim was to identify the various factors that cause time over-runs in construction projects in India and to see the factors which contribute significantly towards the delays for the Indian scenario using inputs from industry experts. A survey of the industry experts was conducted and the Relative Importance Index (RII) was used to rank the most common delay causing factors. The most common factors that cause delays were identified from the literature and then were grouped into 7 categories and these are consultant, contractor, equipment, external, labour, materials and owner related factors. The overall results indicated that the most important factors causing time overruns in construction projects are delay in payments, shortage of equipment and ineffective planning and scheduling.

Similarly, Mali & Warudkar (2016) investigated the causes of delay in construction industry in Pune City in India, using a questionnaire as a data collection instrument and the Average Index (A.I.) as a data analysis technique. Their analysis indicates that shortage of labour is the most common cause of delay in Pune city. In another Indian study, Al-Hammadi & Nawab (2016), analysed delay factors in construction projects. They employed a questionnaire for data collection and used the Weighted Averages (W.A) index for data analysis. Their results indicate that finance, materials and documents related factors are amongst the most common delay factors in construction projects. Furthermore, still in India, Awari *et al* (2016) analysed the cause of delay in construction industry in Mumbai Region, using questionnaire as data collection instruments and the RII as an analysis technique. Their results show that the most important cause in construction project delays include contractor's payment by the owner, design change by the owner or consultant during construction and slow decision making amongst other factors.

Obodoh & Obodoh (2016), in Nigeria, studied the causes and effects of construction project delays. Data was collected using questionnaires and analysed using the RII index. Their findings indicated that insufficient equipment, inaccurate time estimates, interim payment difficulties, change orders and inaccurate cost estimate are amongst the top 10 most significant factors that

contribute to delays in Nigerian construction industry.

Samarghandi *et al* (2016), investigating Iran, a developing Middle Eastern country, focused on the reasons for construction project delays. Several interviews were conducted with owners, contractors, consultants, industry experts and regulatory bodies to accurately ascertain specific delay factors. A questionnaire survey was also carried out for data collection. Data analysis was done using the Severity Index (SI), the Relative Importance Index (RII) and Simple Linear Regression (SLR) to quantitatively determine each delay factor's importance in construction project management. Delay factors were categorized under four major classes (owner defects, contractor defects, consultant defects and law, regulation and other general defects) and the most significant delay factors in each class were determined. The overall results show that the most significant delay factors are: lack of attention to inflation, inefficient budgeting schedule, inaccurate budgeting and resource planning, weak cash flow, inaccurate pricing and bidding, inaccurate first draft and inaccuracies in technical documents, outdated standard mandatory items in cost lists, outdated mandatory terms in contracts and weak governmental budgeting.

In the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Atout (2016), investigated delays caused by project consultants and designers in construction. The study employed a questionnaire survey approach for data collection and relied on severity rating for data analysis. The results indicate that discrepancies of contract documents, incomplete drawings and inspection procedure process are amongst the most important causes of delay.

Elhaniash & Stevovic (2016) conducted a study to identify the factors of delays in construction industry of Libya. The data was collected from survey of 300 respondents involved in management of construction projects including consultants, project managers and owners. The data about delays consisted of three factors: project specific, external and human factors. Correlation and regression analysis techniques were used to find the factor contributing to delays. Among the three factors, human factors and project specific factors were found to be the most important factors that contribute towards delays in construction industry of Libya.

Similarly, in Jordan, Samarah & Bekr (2016) looked at causes and effects of delay in public construction projects. They used a questionnaire survey for data collection and data analysis was done using the Importance Index (I.I), the Frequency Index (F.I), and the Severity Index (S.I). Their results show that inadequate management and supervision by the contractor is the number one cause of delay while the main effects of delay were identified as time and cost overrun.

More recently, Al-Emad *et al* (2017); ranked delay factors for Makkah's construction industry in Saudi Arabia. A questionnaire survey was employed and the Average Index (A.I) was used for data analysis. Their study revealed that poor coordination between parties, shortages of manpower, delays in producing documents, low productivity of labour and unqualified workforce

are amongst the 10 most significant factors causing construction delay in Makkah's construction industry.

In another recent study, Durdyev *et al* (2017) looked at causes of delay in residential construction projects in Cambodia. The study employed a survey approach and data analysis was done using the RII index. Their results showed that shortage of materials on site, unrealistic project scheduling, late delivery of materials, shortage of skilled labour, complexity of project, labour absenteeism, late payment by the owner of completed work, poor site management, delay by subcontractor, accidents due to poor site safety are the major causes of delay in Cambodia. In yet another recent study, this time in Zimbabwe, Nyoni & Bonga (2017) studied factors affecting delays in construction projects in Zimbabwe; and collected their data using questionnaires while the RII index was used to analyze data. Their results indicate that progress payment by owner and change orders are amongst the most important delay factors in Zimbabwe.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the study is three-fold, that is literature review, interviews and questionnaire survey. The first stage was literature review. Thirty-seven (37), delay factors were identified based on both literature review and interviews. The causes of delay were grouped into 6 categories and these are consultant, contractor, labour, materials, equipment and owner related factors.

In the second stage, interviews were conducted. The final stage consisted of a questionnaire survey which was conducted to quantitatively confirm the list of causes and effects obtained from interviews. Section A had thirty-seven (37) structured questions; these are the delay causes which were identified from both literature review and interviews and categorized into six (6) groups namely consultant, contractor, labour, material, equipment and owner related factors.

The questions in this section were measured using a 5-point Likert scale comprising of weightings from 1 to 5; where 1 denotes the least weight while 5 indicates the highest weight. The respondents were asked to rate the causes of delay in their own opinion. Section B had eleven (11) structured questions; these are the delay effects identified from both literature review and interviews. Section C consisted of only one (1) question, designed in a special way so as to capture "other" causes and effects or the so-called omitted variables, the ones that were not identified by the researcher in the pre-selected causes and effects of delay but still exist to affect residential construction projects. Section D had the demographics of the respondents such as age, sex, education and work experience. In order to facilitate the sampling of respondents that are easily accessible during the study, convenience sampling was employed.

Reliability and validity are important concepts in research as they are used for enhancing the accuracy of the assessment and evaluation of a research work (Tavakol & Dennik, 2011). In this study, reliability was checked through checking questionnaires for errors and obvious mistakes

(Creswell, 2014) as well as checking the clarity and appropriateness of questions. Validity, on the other hand was checked through peer debriefing as well as documenting clearly the flow and processing of the data. An external auditor was also engaged to review the entire study. This individual, as already noted by Creswell (2014), is not familiar with the study and can be objective in the evaluation of the research.

3.1 Data Analysis Approach

Data analysis was done using the Relative Importance Index (RII) analysis technique. The following formula used by Nyoni and Bonga (2016 & 2017) was adopted:

$$RII (\%) = \left[\frac{(5n_5 + 4n_4 + 3n_3 + 2n_2 + n_1)}{5(n_5 + n_4 + n_3 + n_2 + n_1)} \right] \times 100\% \quad \text{-----(1)}$$

Where n1, n2, n3, n4, and n5 are the number of respondents who selected: (1) very weak, (2) weak, (3) fair, (4) strong and (5) very strong.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A total of 79 questionnaires were distributed to consultants, owners, contractors and construction sector professionals in the city of Harare, Zimbabwe via hand delivery as well as via email. 63 questionnaires were completed and analyzed, giving a response rate of approximately 80%. The following table shows the RII ranking of delay causes in residential construction projects in the city of Harare.

Table 1 Causes of Delay in Residential Construction Projects in Harare

TABLE I. Causes of Delay	TABLE II. Category	Cat	TABLE III. RII Index	RII	TABLE IV. Within Rank	W	TABLE V. Overall Rank	O
TABLE VI. Poor financial control on site	TABLE VII. Contractor related	Con	TABLE VIII.	93.4	TABLE IX.	1	TABLE X.	1
TABLE XI. Inefficient budgeting schedule	TABLE XII. Owner related	Ow	TABLE XIII.	92.9	TABLE XIV.	1	TABLE XV.	2
TABLE XVI. Ineffective site management	TABLE XVII. Owner related	Ow	TABLE XVIII.	90.1	TABLE XIX.	2	TABLE XX.	3
TABLE XXI. Inadequate project management assistance	TABLE XXII. Consultant related	Con	TABLE XXIII.	89.6	TABLE XXIV.	1	TABLE XXV.	4
TABLE XXVI. Inaccurate pricing and bidding	TABLE XXVII. Contractor related	Con	TABLE XXVIII.	89.7	TABLE XXIX.	2	TABLE XXX.	5
TABLE XXXI. Having too many	TABLE XXXII. Consultant related	Con	TABLE XXXIII.	88.3	TABLE XXXIV.	2	TABLE XXXV.	6

unforeseen items in cost lists						
TABLE XXXVI. Unreliable sub-contractor	TABLE XXXVII. Contractor related	Con	TABLE XXXVIII. 86.5	TABLE XXXIX. 3	TABLE XL. 7	
TABLE XLI. Rework due to errors	TABLE XLII. Contractor related	Con	TABLE XLIII. 85.8	TABLE XLIV. 4	TABLE XLV. 8	
TABLE XLVI. Delay in performing inspection and testing	TABLE XLVII. Consultant related	Con	TABLE XLVIII. 84.3	TABLE XLIX. 3	TABLE L. 9	
TABLE LI. Inaccurate technical drawings such as mechanical or electrical drawings	TABLE LII. Consultant related	Con	TABLE LIII. 80.2	TABLE LIV. 4	TABLE LV. 10	
TABLE LVI. Too many change orders	TABLE LVII. Owner related	Ow	TABLE LVIII. 79.7	TABLE LIX. 3	TABLE LX. 11	
TABLE LXI. Inaccurate site investigation	TABLE LXII. Consultant related	Con	TABLE LXIII. 75.4	TABLE LXIV. 5	TABLE LXV. 12	
TABLE LXVI. Frequent change of sub-contractor	TABLE LXVII. Contractor related	Con	TABLE LXVIII. 75.1	TABLE LXIX. 5	TABLE LXX. 13	
TABLE LXXI. Delay in obtaining permits	TABLE LXXII. Owner related	Ow	TABLE LXXIII. 74.9	TABLE LXXIV. 4	TABLE LXXV. 14	
TABLE LXXVI. Shortage of materials	TABLE LXXVII. Materials related	Mat	TABLE LXXVIII. 73.3	TABLE LXXIX. 1	TABLE LXXX. 15	
TABLE LXXXI. Shortage of equipment	TABLE LXXXII. Equipment related	Equ	TABLE LXXXIII. 71.8	TABLE LXXXIV. 1	TABLE LXXXV. 16	
TABLE LXXXVI. Low productivity of labour	TABLE LXXXVII. Labour related	Lab	TABLE LXXXVIII. 70.6	TABLE LXXXIX. 1	TABLE XC. 17	
TABLE XCI. Delay in updating project status	TABLE XCII. Consultant related	Con	TABLE XCIII. 69.4	TABLE XCIV. 6	TABLE XCV. 18	
TABLE XCVI. Low efficiency of equipment	TABLE XCVII. Equipment related	Equ	TABLE XCVIII. 69.2	TABLE XCIX. 2	TABLE C. 19	
TABLE CI. Obsolete technology	TABLE CII. Contractor related	Con	TABLE CIII. 67.5	TABLE CIV. 6	TABLE CV. 20	
TABLE CVI. Frequent equipment breakdown	TABLE CVII. Equipment related	Equ	TABLE CVIII. 65.8	TABLE CIX. 3	TABLE CX. 21	
TABLE CXI. Adherence to outdated construction methods	TABLE CXII. Contractor related	Con	TABLE CXIII. 64.6	TABLE CXIV. 7	TABLE CXV. 22	
TABLE CXVI. Absenteeism	TABLE CXVII. Labour related	Lab	TABLE CXVIII. 61.9	TABLE CXIX. 2	TABLE CXX. 23	
TABLE CXXI. Incompetent project team	TABLE CXXII. Contractor related	Con	TABLE CXXIII. 60.2	TABLE CXXIV. 8	TABLE CXXV. 24	
TABLE CXXVI. Assigning inexperienced personnel to supervisory duties	TABLE CXXVII. Consultant related	Con	TABLE CXXVIII. 59.6	TABLE CXXIX. 7	TABLE CXXX. 25	
TABLE CXXXI. Labour injuries	TABLE CXXXII. Labour related	Lab	TABLE CXXXIII. 57.7	TABLE CXXXIV. 3	TABLE CXXXV. 26	

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TABLE CXXXVI. Lack of accuracy in revising feasibility studies	TABLE CXXXVII. Consultant related	TABLE CXXXVIII. 52.4	TABLE CXXXIX. 8	TABLE CXL. 27
TABLE CXLI. Unreliable suppliers	TABLE CXLII. Materials related	TABLE CXLIII. 49.7	TABLE CXLIV. 2	TABLE CXLV. 28
TABLE CXLVI. Changes in material type and specification	TABLE CXLVII. Materials related	TABLE CXLVIII. 47.4	TABLE CXLIX. 3	TABLE CL. 29
TABLE CLI. Conflicts between consultant and design engineer	TABLE CLII. Consultant related	TABLE CLIII. 46.8	TABLE CLIV. 9	TABLE CLV. 30
TABLE CLVI. Shortage of labour	TABLE CLVII. Labour related	TABLE CLVIII. 46.2	TABLE CLIX. 4	TABLE CLX. 31
TABLE CLXI. Poor quality of construction materials	TABLE CLXII. Materials related	TABLE CLXIII. 43.9	TABLE CLXIV. 4	TABLE CLXV. 32
TABLE CLXVI. Late delivery of materials	TABLE CLXVII. Materials related	TABLE CLXVIII. 41.5	TABLE CLXIX. 5	TABLE CLXX. 33
TABLE CLXXI. Personal conflicts among labour	TABLE CLXXII. Labour related	TABLE CLXXIII. 39.3	TABLE CLXXIV. 5	TABLE CLXXV. 34
TABLE CLXXVI. Labour strikes	TABLE CLXXVII. Labour related	TABLE CLXXVIII. 39.1	TABLE CLXXIX. 6	TABLE CLXXX. 35
TABLE CLXXXI. Escalation of material prices	TABLE CLXXXII. Materials related	TABLE CLXXXIII. 37.4	TABLE CLXXXIV. 6	TABLE CLXXXV. 36
TABLE CLXXXVI. Lack of knowledge about regulations	TABLE CLXXXVII. Owner related	TABLE CLXXXVIII. 33.6	TABLE CLXXXIX. 5	TABLE CXC. 37

The table above shows that there are only 27 factors which have an RII index which is above 50%. This effectively means that the 27 highly ranked factors are more important as compared to the lowly ranked factors. As clearly shown in the table above, the most important cause of delay in residential construction projects in the city of Harare in Zimbabwe is poor financial control on site. Zimbabwe is currently facing a serious cash crisis and project managers as well as other stakeholders should use financial resources sparingly if project success is to be achieved.

Other important delay factors identified include but are not limited to inefficient budgeting schedule, ineffective site management, inadequate project management assistance, inaccurate pricing and bidding, as well as having too many unforeseen items in the costs list. However, the least important delay factor was found to be lack of knowledge about regulations, as shown by an RII index of 33.6%. This effectively means that most players in the construction sector in Zimbabwe are fully aware of regulations of the industry despite the fact the construction sector in Zimbabwe does not have a fully separate construction industry policy.

Thanks to the government of Zimbabwe since the policy is currently being crafted and expected to be operationalized any time soon. Another less important delay factor is the escalation of material prices. This could be attributed to the fact that the economy of Zimbabwe, while literally

bedridden, is also stuck between cash crisis and deflation. Observation shows that prices of most commodities are going down rather than up. Inflation is still hovering in its negative territory; therefore escalation of material prices is a rare case. Other less important delay factors include but are not limited to labour strikes, personal conflicts amongst labour, late delivery of materials, poor quality of construction materials as well as shortage of labour.

4.1 Effects of delay in residential construction projects in the city of Harare, Zimbabwe

Figure 1 below shows the effects of delays in residential construction projects in Harare, Zimbabwe:

Figure 1 Effects of Delay in Residential Construction Projects in Harare

In the above figure, the effects of delays are: time overrun, increase in the final cost of the project, wastages and underutilization of manpower, reduced profits, arbitration, litigation, disputes between parties, reduced economic growth, frustration and dissatisfaction of clients, tying down of client capital due to non-completion and total abandonment of projects in chronological order. All the effects of delay, as shown in the figure above, each bears an RII index which is well above 50%, indicating that all the identified effects of delay are quite important.

4.2 Methods of minimizing delays in construction:

- I. Owners should minimize changes in project design
- II. Project goals should be clearly stated to all parties
- III. Frequent site meetings of all parties
- IV. Proper utilization of modern construction technology
- V. Proper and timely procurement of materials
- VI. Effective planning
- VII. Proper project scheduling
- VIII. Collaborative working in construction
- IX. Clients should clearly set their requirements to reduce mistakes and errors in projects
- X. Proper estimation of initial project cost
- XI. Contractor should make sure that they have enough financial resources to execute projects
- XII. Consultant should immediately correct their design errors to avoid delays
- XIII. All projects stakeholders should work together to ensure that all disputes are mitigated properly and timely to avoid prolonging scheduled contract duration during litigation processes.

5. CONCLUSION

The current study looked at the different causes and effects of delay in residential construction projects in Zimbabwe. From literature review and interview of construction industry experts, thirty-seven (37) causes of delay in six (6) different groups were evaluated. Eleven (11) effects of delay were also identified and assessed. The Relative Importance Index (RII) technique was used for data analysis. The study found that poor financial control on site; ineffective budgeting schedule and ineffective site management are amongst the highly ranked factors causing delays in residential construction projects in Harare. The results also indicate that the most important effects of delays in residential construction projects in Harare are time overrun and increase in the final cost of the project. However, the study also managed to come up with possible solutions to mitigate delays in residential construction projects in the city of Harare and Zimbabwe at large. Construction managers and policy makers are encouraged to take note of all the identified delay factors; however, highly ranked delay factors can be prioritized on the basis that they are generally more important than lowly ranked factors.

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